

Organizational Justice on Employee Behavior at Private Service Companies in Myanmar

*Khin Nyein Su¹, Zin Ko Ko², Nan Wai Linn³, Yin Ko Ko⁴, Thida Lwin @ Thida Oo⁵

^{1,5}Doctorate Degree Scholar, Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) Mandalay, Myanmar.

²Founder & Chancellor, Myanmar Commercial University (MCU), 63(C), Between 27 x 28 Street, Mandalay, Myanmar.

³Vice Principal & Registrar, Myanmar Commercial University (MCU), 63(C), Between 27 x 28 Street, Mandalay, Myanmar.

⁴Director, Myanmar Commercial University (MCU), 63(C), Between 27 x 28 Street, Mandalay, Myanmar.

*Corresponding author: [Khin Nyein Su](#)

Doctorate Degree Scholar, Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) Mandalay, Myanmar.

Abstract

This study seeks to examine the organizational factors that impact the perceived organizational justice of employees in private companies in Myanmar. Additionally, it aims to explore how the leader-member exchange relationship and organizational support mediate the relationship between organizational justice and employee behavior. The study is conducted with a group of 550 employees that work in private enterprises in Myanmar. Quantitative data can be analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics, such as multiple linear regression and the Hayes Process Macro for mediation analysis. This study examined the impact of organizational practices, such as empowerment and involvement, compensation and rewards, performance appraisal, consistency, conflict management, and power distance on perceptions of organizational justice (specifically distributive, procedural, and interactional justice) Additionally, this study investigates the impact of organizational justice on employee behavior. This study also investigates the role of leader-member exchange connection and organizational support in mediating the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior. As a result of correlation analysis, organizational characteristics are strongly and significantly correlated with organizational justice. Then distributive justice, procedural justice, interactional justice, leader member exchange relationship, organizational support, and organizational justice are directly correlated, but their association is weak. The study's findings indicate that empowerment, rewards, and consistency have a significant and favorable impact on distributive justice. Distributive justice has a detrimental impact on power distance. Procedural fairness has a favorable and significant impact on empowerment, performance rating, and consistency. The impact of performance appraisal and conflict management on interpersonal justice is both positive and significant. Informational justice has a favorable and considerable impact on conflict management and consistency. The results of the study showed that empowerment, remuneration and incentive, performance appraisal, conflict management, and consistency were important factors that predicted overall organizational justice. Nevertheless, power distance was not identified as a decisive element in determining organizational fairness. The findings of this study indicate that organizational justice has a statistically significant and favorable impact on employee behaviors, namely in-role behavior, organizational citizenship conduct towards individuals, and organizational citizenship behavior towards the corporation. Nevertheless, the coefficient of the regression analysis for these behaviors was determined to be insignificant. This study revealed that the association between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior is partially mediated by leader-member exchange relationship and organizational support. The study provides a valuable and original contribution to the existing literature by demonstrating the factors that lead to organizational justice. It also explores the role of leader-member exchange relationship and organizational support in mediating the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior.

Keywords: Distributive Justice, Procedural Justice, Interactional Justice, leader-member exchange relationship, organizational support, Organizational Citizenship Behavior.

1. INTRODUCTION

Employees, including those in the human resources department, are widely recognized as a crucial asset within a firm, playing a pivotal role in attaining a competitive edge. Furthermore, it is widely acknowledged that the proficient administration of individuals inside organizational settings plays a crucial role in effectively adapting to dynamic and vibrant situations, ultimately leading to the achievement of superior organizational outcomes (Kehoe & Wright, 2013). In a reciprocal manner, it is imperative for enterprises to prioritize the cultivation and effective management of their human resources. Rather than perceiving persons solely as resources, organizations should adopt a perspective that positions them as beneficiaries of their services. This approach, as advocated by Patterson (2001), enables firms to gain a comprehensive understanding of the needs, expectations, and behaviors of their employees. Perceived organizational justice, also known as perceived fairness, has emerged as a crucial element in the field of human resources management (HRM) and a flourishing area of study within organizational behavior.

In recent decades, the concept of organizational justice (OJ) has emerged as a significant factor in shaping and evaluating work-related responses, behaviors, and attitudes, with the aim of enhancing the overall quality of workers' work experiences. Numerous scholarly works in the field of organizational behavior have acknowledged the importance of employee perceptions of equity, justice, and fairness inside their respective businesses as influential factors in shaping employee attitudes and behaviors (Frenkel & Bednall, 2016; Ha & Ha, 2015; Rai, 2015; Shan, Ishaq, & Shaheen, 2015). Hence, the concept of "organizational justice" pertains to the perceptions held by employees on the degree of fairness exhibited in the decisions and acts of management. This view, in turn, has the potential to impact employees' attitudes towards management. The perception of fairness holds significant importance within organizations, as it has a profound impact on organizational performance and success. The manner in which employees perceive justice plays a crucial role in fostering trust between employers and employees, hence enhancing the level of employees' citizenship behavior. Saifi and Shahzad (2017) suggest that organizational justice exerts a notable and favorable influence on organizational citizenship behavior.

Contemporary organizations are currently striving to cultivate an environment that fosters employee motivation and self-improvement. This is achieved by not just emphasizing job responsibilities, but also by promoting the development of employees' organizational citizenship behaviors (OCB). Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) refers to the voluntary actions of employees that go beyond their prescribed job responsibilities inside the workplace. These actions are recognized and rewarded by the firm as a means of acknowledging the tasks that have been accomplished (Paramita, 2012). Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) plays a vital role in the achievement of organizational success. For instance, when employees perceive a discrepancy between their input and the desired outcomes, it can lead to a decline in their inclination to engage in OCB. Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) can be classified into two distinct categories: organizational citizenship behaviors towards the organization (OCBO) and organizational citizenship behaviors towards individuals, primarily supervisors (OCBI/OCBS), particularly when these activities are directed towards benefiting supervisors. Organ et al. (2006) correctly recognized organizational citizenship behavior as a significant determinant of organizational performance and success.

Conversely, the conduct exhibited by employees can be attributed to the positive nature of their relationship with their supervisor. A limited number of recent studies in the domain of organizational justice have focused on the inclusion of mediating variables in examining the association between justice and its results. Social exchange theory is a prominent framework for understanding the psychological responses of employees in relation to their impression of organizational justice. Hence, it is crucial to ascertain the mediating effect of the leader-member exchange connection and the moderating role of perceived organizational support in the context of examining the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior in this study.

The notion of Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) posits that leaders and followers establish distinct relationships characterized by social exchanges. Based on the tenets of leader-member exchange (LMX) theory, it is posited that supervisors establish distinct connections with individual employees, wherein high-quality relationships are distinguished by attributes such as respect, trust, and mutual advantage (Volmer, 2011). Organizations may gain a competitive advantage in personnel retention and motivation through the cultivation of high-quality leader-member exchange relationships. Perceived organizational support (POS) refers to the employee's perception that the organization places importance on their contributions, prioritizes their well-being, and is consistently prepared to offer resources to facilitate their effective task performance.

The primary objective of this study is to identify the factors that influence employees' perceptions of justice. Specifically, the study focuses on individual personality traits and human resource management practices as potential antecedents of organizational justice, including distributive, procedural, and interactional justice. These factors have been chosen based on their potential associations with organizational justice and their significance in organizational operations. The present study aims to establish a significant connection between the elements influencing antecedents and organizational fairness. So, the overall purpose of the study is to examine the impact of personality and human

resource management practices on employees' justice perceptions (i.e. Distributive, procedural, and interactional) and the extent to which these perceptions affect important organizational outcomes (i.e. organizational citizenship behavior) of private service companies employees in Myanmar.

2. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

The notion of organizational justice (OJ) is widely discussed and recognized in Myanmar; yet, its empirical validity has yet to be established. The perception of organizational justice has a substantial impact on employee work outcomes, since fair treatment is associated with more favorable attitudes, behaviors, and job outcomes. The impression of organizational justice (OJ) has a significant impact on several employee work outcomes, such as organizational citizenship behavior, commitment, job involvement, and performance. The present study incorporates an examination of these behavioral consequences.

The efficacy of the company is primarily contingent upon the behaviors exhibited by its employees. The diminished level of citizenship behaviors among employees in Myanmar can be attributed to several factors. These include the country's long-standing history of nontransparent bureaucracy, unfair labor practices, lack of adherence to labor laws within organizations, prioritization of individual department interests over organizational goals, unjust assessment of employee performance without clear objectives and key result areas, absence of regular performance evaluations, bias in providing opportunities, job insecurity, limited career growth prospects, high unemployment rates, and restricted choices in the personal lives of employees.

A significant number of firms in Myanmar encounter this particular challenge, indicating that employees tend to exhibit in-role conduct while demonstrating a lesser inclination towards engaging in extra-role actions. In recent years, there has been a significant proliferation of global firms, resulting in a substantial increase in job opportunities for employees. Studying employee habits in the private sector of Myanmar holds significant value due to its current state of rapid growth and development.

In order to optimize organizational development, it is imperative for managers to possess a comprehensive understanding and awareness of the pivotal role that employees play in driving the success of the firm. Efforts should be made to identify strategies and methods that can enhance performance at both the individual and organizational levels. Organizations should not solely focus on the recruitment and retention of highly dedicated personnel, but should also strive to elicit their employees' behaviors in order to effectively navigate the fluctuations within the dynamic business environment.

Employee behaviors are highly influenced by employees' perception of organizational justice. Fairness or justice is a fundamental concept in human social interaction. Organizations always make efforts to achieve sustainable growth and development by maintaining smooth social interaction with its employees. Organizational justice refers to employee perception of fairness in the organization and the significance of organizational justice has been recognized as a basic requirement for the effective functioning of organization. Sometimes organizations do not do justice (interactional, distributive, and procedural) with its people and therefore they fail to achieve their desired outcome (obedience, participation, loyalty). Feeling of injustice creates tension among employees and they start stealing in the name of the organization. Mostly organizations are not considering the importance of organizational justice and that is why they are failing in achieving their employee's extra-role behavior.

The behaviors exhibited by employees are significantly impacted by their impression of organizational fairness. The notion of fairness or justice holds significant importance in the realm of human social interaction. Organizations consistently strive to attain sustainable growth and development through the establishment of effective social interactions with their personnel. Organizational justice pertains to the subjective evaluation of fairness by employees inside an organization. The importance of organizational justice has been widely acknowledged as a fundamental prerequisite for the efficient operation of an organization. In certain instances, organizations may fall short in providing equitable treatment to its members in terms of interactional, distributive, and procedural justice, resulting in their inability to attain the desired outcomes of obedience, participation, and loyalty. The experience of perceiving injustice within an organizational context can engender a state of tension among employees, leading some individuals to engage in acts of theft under the guise of acting on behalf of the firm. Many firms tend to overlook the significance of organizational justice, leading to their failure in fostering employee engagement in extra-role behavior.

Nowadays, in the competitive world, organizations need employees whom performance goes beyond their traditional job descriptions or formal duties as a vital source of organizational effectiveness. On the other hand, employees exhibit higher levels of performance and act more than their job descriptions when they believe they are treated fairly at workplace. In other words, employee's job performance may increase or decrease in relation to perceptions of inequitable outcomes. Fair treatment promotes the work motives and enhances performance at workplace.

Based on this, two important organizational concepts will be recognized which here after are called as organizational citizenship behavior and organizational justice.

In the contemporary day, within the context of a highly competitive global landscape, businesses are increasingly reliant on individuals whose performance extends beyond the confines of their conventional job descriptions or formal responsibilities, serving as a crucial catalyst for enhancing organizational success. In contrast, when individuals perceive fair treatment in the workplace, they tend to demonstrate elevated levels of performance and engage in behaviors that extend beyond the scope of their job descriptions. Put simply, the job performance of employees can be influenced by their views of unfair outcomes, leading to either an increase or decrease in performance. The promotion of equitable treatment within the workplace fosters employee motivation and contributes to improved performance. Based on the aforementioned information, two significant organizational ideas will be identified, namely organizational citizenship behavior and organizational justice.

Numerous studies have been conducted to recognize the significance of organizational justice in attaining organizational objectives and goals through employee citizenship behavior. This form of behavior is not explicitly outlined in employees' job descriptions and is contingent upon their personal discretion. In order to exhibit such behavior, employees require a sense of purpose and a robust perception of fairness. The presence of justice has been found to have a positive impact on job performance, while its absence can lead to increased tension among individuals. This tension, in turn, may result in less job commitment, reduced job satisfaction, lower job performance, and a reluctance to assist co-workers.

The objective of this study is to investigate the effects of organizational justice on employee behaviors, namely in-role conduct and organizational citizenship behavior, via the lens of justice theories. This examination takes into account the potential mediating role of leader-member exchange relationship (LMX) and the moderating influence of organizational support. The objective of this study is to examine the notion of organizational justice within the broader service industries, without specific emphasis on any one sector. The purpose is to provide a complete comprehension of the issues, commonalities, and potential resolutions pertaining to justice within this extensive and heterogeneous domain.

3. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The problem of the study can be represented in the following key research questions:

1. How employees perceived of organizational justice?
2. How do individual factors of personality influence on organizational justice of employees at private service companies in Myanmar?
3. How do human resource management practices influence on organizational justice of employees at private service companies in Myanmar?
4. How can organizational justice contribute to the performance and behaviors of employees at private service companies in Myanmar?
5. How do Leader- member exchange relationship (LMX) mediate between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior of employees at private service companies in Myanmar?
6. How do organizational support moderate between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior of employees at private service companies in Myanmar?

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between organizational justice and employee behaviors considering the concept of organizational justice as a single construct and to examine the mediating effects of organizational support and leader member exchange relationship in generating the outcomes of employee performance and behaviors in the context of private service companies' sector in Myanmar. The following are the specific objectives.

1. To find out the employees' perception of organizational justice using four different dimensions such as distributive, procedural, interpersonal, and informational justice under the single construct as a higher order factor.
2. To analyze the influence of individual factor (personality) on employees' perceptions of organizational justice at private service companies in Myanmar
3. To analyze the influence of human resource management practices on employees' perceptions of organizational justice of employees at private service companies in Myanmar.
4. To determine the effect of organizational justice on in-role and extra-role employee behaviors (both of OCBI and OCBO) of private service companies in Myanmar.
5. To examine whether leader-member exchange relationship mediate between organizational justice and respective employee behaviors of private services companies in Myanmar.
6. To examine whether organizational support moderate the relationship between organizational justice and respective employee behaviors of private services companies in Myanmar.

5. METHOD OF STUDY

The primary data will be collected from the employees of private service companies in Myanmar. Convenience sampling method will be used, with a total of 650 employees from private service companies' employees. Descriptive analysis was used to analyze the background of sample of employees. Questionnaire survey method is used to collect the primary data from private service companies' employees in Myanmar. This study employs quantitative research method using structural equation modeling (SEM) in SPSS to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation, normality and reliability are tested before proceeding to SEM.

6. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The selection criteria for data collectors in this study will be limited to personnel of private service companies who have obtained a Master of Business Administration (MBA) degree. In order to enhance the generalizability of the findings, it would have been advantageous to include a broader range of sectors within the sample. The study does not encompass the manufacturing sectors.

This study used a unified construct that encompasses the four dimensions of justice, rather than analyzing the regression with each individual facet of the construct separately. The concept of overall organization justice, which is a higher-level construct comprising four distinct dimensions of justice (namely, distributive justice, procedural justice, interpersonal justice, and informational justice), is employed to examine the association between leader-member exchange relationships and employee behaviors and the role of organizational support on employee behaviors.

Several limitations were identified in the present investigation. Initially, with regards to employee performance or in-role activities, the data collected from employees was limited to self-rated responses. To mitigate any bias, it would be advantageous to have access to objective data or supervisor-rated scores. Furthermore, the study employed organizational justice measures to assess employees' perceptions of justice inside the business and their perceptions of the quality of their relationship with supervisors. The act of perception may exhibit a proclivity to diverge from objective reality due to inherent human tendencies. Nevertheless, the focus of this research pertains to examining the impact of employee views of justice on their behaviors. Consequently, employing perceptions as a measure would not pose any issues. Furthermore, the analysis of the data was conducted solely using cross-sectional data. To ascertain the causative outcome, employing longitudinal data would be more advantageous.

7. LITERATURE REVIEW

7.1 CONCEPT OF ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE

According to Greenberg (1990a), the initial theories on social justice in organizations mostly emphasized broader social interactions rather than specifically addressing organizational contexts. In the realm of workplace dynamics, there has been a recent emergence of conceptual models aimed at elucidating the concept of fairness. Justice is evaluated based on two fundamental principles: equilibrium and accuracy. These principles assess the equilibrium and accuracy of decisions, procedures, and actions, guaranteeing their alignment with perceived correctness. The field of organizational justice research primarily examines the reactions of employees to the outcomes they receive and the techniques employed to attain these objectives. Scholars make a distinction between distributive justice, which pertains to the substance of decisions, and procedural justice, which centers on the procedures used in decision-making (Greenberg, 1990a).

Researchers have provided varying definitions for the concept of organizational justice. According to Okocha and Anyanwu (2016), the concept of organizational justice pertains to the consideration of equity inside the workplace. It involves an evaluation of an institution's treatment of its employees, with due regard to overarching moral and ethical principles. The concept encompasses the extent to which employees in an organization adopt and support managerial practices (Ali, 2016). Justice is commonly understood as a morally upright course of action or decision, based on principles of ethics, religious beliefs, impartiality, egalitarianism, or legal norms. Kalay (2016) provided an expansive conceptualization of organizational justice. The author characterizes organizational justice as an assessment of managerial decisions pertaining to employee management, encompassing aspects such as the allocation of responsibilities, empowerment practices, wage structures, distribution of rewards, equitable economic and social work policies, employees' perception of the overall internal decision-making process, and the extent to which these decisions are communicated to employees within the workplace. Organizational justice pertains to the evaluation made by employees regarding the fairness of their treatment in the context of their employment, and the subsequent implications of this evaluation on other work-related factors inside the workplace (Okocha and Anyanwu, 2016). The present study is grounded in the concept of organizational justice, which is conceptualized as a unifying latent construct including four distinct dimensions: distributive, procedural, informational, and interpersonal justice.

a) Distributive Justices

Based on the ratio of inputs to outcomes received from employer organizations—a cognitive comparison with referents in the same entity or similar organizations elsewhere—employees determine whether an exchange relationship is fair or unfair. This type of organizational justice is derived from the theory of equity promoted by Adams (1965).

Three presumptions or principles of distributive justice were established by Organ (1988), including the following: the principle of equity, which stipulates that a person's compensation should be commensurate with their contribution; The equality principle states that every person should have an equal chance to acquire rewards, regardless of their attributes; The distribution of resources in accordance with each person's needs is known as the "principle of need." Distributive justice is justified by each person's opinion of fairness in relation to the results or incentives they obtain at work (Colquitt, 2001). According to study, people constantly compare their contributions to the results of others in the company. If the ratio is equal, they sense equality; if it is not equal, they perceive injustice (Jawahar, 2002). According to Hassan (2002), personal outcomes like job satisfaction are indicators of distributive justice. He goes on to say that an unfair distribution of rewards based on inputs will cause stress and reduce work output for the individual. Distributive justice discusses the results of justice an individual receives from the institution by focusing on incentives and sanctions that result in work performance (Nirmala and Akhilesh, 2006).

b) Procedural Justice

Organizations establish procedural frameworks that provide guidance to managers in their decision-making processes pertaining to resource allocation, staff promotions, transfers, and performance evaluations. Procedural fairness is a moral principle that emphasizes the use of fair procedures to allocate outcomes to individuals within organizations, without any hint of bias (George & Jones, 2006). According to Colquitt and Chertkoff (2000), procedural justice refers to the implementation of fair and equitable policies in areas such as payments, decision-making, and knowledge sharing inside an organization. This concept is also associated with the perception of fairness among members of the organization, as discussed by Konovsky (2000). Procedural justice encompasses the inclusion of voice in the decision-making process, the consistent application of rules, and the accurate utilization of information to prevent deceit (Greenberg, 2011; Baldwin, 2006).

c) Interactional Justice

According to Bies (2001), persons assess fairness not only based on formal outcomes and procedures, but also through social or communication factors. Colquitt (2001) conducted empirical research to validate the division of interactional justice into two distinct dimensions: interpersonal justice and informational justice.

Interpersonal justice, as defined by Colquitt (2001), refers to the extent to which managers within an organization treat employees with civility, respect, and dignity. The perception of unjust treatment might arise from the evaluation that individuals are not being treated with dignity and respect (Bies & Moag, 1986; Colquitt, 2001; Greenberg, 1993).

The concept of informational justice, often known as INFJ, pertains to the provision of information that is sufficient, accurate, and timely to individuals. When employees see that information is inaccurate or not provided in a timely manner, and when they feel that sufficient explanations are lacking, it might result in perceptions of unfair treatment (Bies & Moag, 1986; Colquitt, 2001; Greenberg, 1993). Bies and Moag (1986) introduced a conceptual framework comprising two distinct criteria for assessing the concept of informational justice. These criteria encompass the notions of honesty and justification. Shapiro, Buttner, and Barry (1994) conducted a study on the perceived adequacy of explanation. In their research, they suggested the inclusion of further variables, including the reasonableness, timeliness, and specificity of the information.

7.2 PERCEPTIONS OF JUSTICE AND SOCIAL EXCHANGE THEORY

Blau (1964) introduced social exchange theory (SET), a compelling theoretical framework for comprehending workers' attitudes and behaviors within an organization. By looking at the non-rational side of human behavior, social exchange theory is a comprehensive framework that supports social exchange theory. It clarifies the relationship between emotive states and logical decision-making, with consequences for the growth of enduring relationships and solidarity. The idea is predicated on the reciprocity principle, which forms the basis of social behaviorism and has been used to the explanation of psychological contracts, networks, social power, and justice. A framework for examining the connection between social exchange and organizational behavior is the Social Exchange Theory. It has been used in a number of disciplines, including psychology, economics, and criminal justice. The idea has been applied to comprehend social exchange's effect on organizational performance as well as the motives, feelings, and actions of both individuals and groups.

According to Cropanzano and Mitchell (2005), this idea holds significant importance in the context of employee relations inside the workplace. The authors of the study propose that specific work factors indicate interpersonal relationships that typically result in advantageous outcomes for the business, such as the cultivation of favorable attitudes and behaviors among employees.

Lambe, Wittmann, and Spekman (2001) have proposed four premises pertaining to this hypothesis. Every interaction involving exchange yields economic and/or social outcomes. A temporal comparison is made between the outcomes achieved in a given exchange and those that could be attained through alternative exchanges. If the outcomes consistently demonstrate positive trends over time, trust in the counterparty strengthens and the commitment to that

particular exchange intensifies. With continued maintenance of this process, relational exchange rules are eventually established to govern the relationship.

In summary, the Social Exchange Theory (SET) posits that in a reciprocal connection, the benefits derived from a constructive contact between two parties need not be solely economic in nature. Rather, these benefits can be influenced by the accumulation of shared experiences and the cultivation of positive attitudes and behaviors between the involved parties. Based on the provided information, this theory suggests that within a working setting, interpersonal behaviors, such as the relationships between individuals and their supervisors or co-workers, are influenced by the exchange of costs and benefits. When employees see that they are receiving benefits from the organization, they experience a sense of obligation to reciprocate by contributing to the enterprise. Eisenberger et al. (1986) and Graen and Scandura (1987) suggest that Social Exchange Theory (SET) encompasses two distinct categories of social transactions. One aspect that is emphasized in organizational research is perceived organizational support (POS), which focuses on the reciprocal interaction between employees and the organization. The second aspect pertains to the exchange that occurs between the leader and member, wherein the supervisor and employee engage in resource sharing as a means of engagement (Lee & Duffy, 2019). The objective of this study is to examine the mediating role of the leader-member exchange relationship and the moderating role of organizational support in the link between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior.

7.3 Antecedents of Justice Perceptions

While there has been considerable study conducted on the consequences of organizational justice, there has been a relative lack of attention given to the antecedents of organizational justice (Cohen Charash & Spector, 2001). The existing body of research on organizational justice has consistently demonstrated that the perception of fairness is associated with a range of ideas that may be effectively categorized based on their level of analysis, namely the person level and the organizational level. This study aims to investigate the relationship between individual levels of personality traits and organizational levels of human resource management practice as predictors of organizational fairness.

(a) Individual Factors

Personality

The primary objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between individual personality traits and the development of justice climates. Over the course of recent decades, scholars have increasingly acknowledged the significance of organizational justice as a crucial factor influencing the well-being and health of employees (Colquitt et al., 2013). According to Greenberg (2001), there exists a suggestion that individuals may not share the same conceptions of fairness and justice. Hence, it is rather perplexing because the underlying reasons behind the variations in individuals' perceptions of organizational fairness remain elusive. Based on prior research findings (Törnroos et al., 2012; Judge, Heller, & Mount, 2002), it is plausible to suggest that personality traits have a significant role in shaping individuals' perceptions of their psychosocial working environment and their work attitudes. Consequently, it is reasonable to hypothesize that personality could serve as a potential explanatory factor for the observed variations in organizational justice perceptions among individuals. While it is generally acknowledged by employees that justice plays a significant role in fostering well-being inside the workplace, the individual interpretation of organizational justice can differ among employees. Personality traits have the potential to impact individuals' perceptions of the work environment in various manners. Specifically, individuals with distinct personality traits may perceive their surroundings differently, resulting in diverse reactions and behaviors (Barsky & Kaplan, 2007; Törnroos et al., 2012). In order to have a comprehensive understanding of the determinants of organizational justice views and to devise strategies for managers to effectively address individual differences, it is imperative to delve deeper into the influence of personality on perceptions of organizational justice.

Five – Factor Model of Personality

The Five-Factor Model (FFM) delineates five overarching dimensions or qualities of personality, namely neuroticism, extraversion, openness, conscientiousness, and agreeableness (McCrae & Costa, 2003). Previous studies have demonstrated a correlation between the Five-Factor Model (FFM) qualities and other work-related factors, such as job satisfaction (Judge et al., 2002), work performance (Barrick & Mount, 1991; Hertz & Donovan, 2000), work motivation (Judge & Ilies, 2002), and work stress (Törnroos et al., 2013). Hence, it may be inferred that the Five-Factor Model (FFM) personality qualities are likely to be linked with individuals' judgments of organizational fairness. The subsequent text provides a fundamental overview of the five personality traits.

Agreeableness

The construct of agreeableness encompasses various traits such as altruism, warmth, generosity, trust, and collaboration, as identified by Costa and McCrae (1992). The subject matter pertains to the levels of courtesy, trustworthiness, and helpfulness exhibited by individuals (Goldberg, 1990). Individuals that exhibit agreeable traits are commonly perceived as possessing qualities such as kindness, compassion, and tolerance, in contrast to individuals who display lower levels of

agreeableness, who are often seen as manipulating, self-centered, and suspicious. According to Sung and Choi (2009), individuals who possess a high level of agreeableness demonstrate a tendency to prioritize the interests of others, actively strive to prevent disputes, and exhibit a greater inclination towards cooperation and offering assistance as a means of preserving existing connections. According to Migliore (2016), those who possess agreeable traits tend to exhibit higher levels of adaptability, whereas those who possess disagreeable traits tend to display a reluctance to engage in social interactions. Agreeable individuals may exhibit behavioral changes in order to accommodate others due to their tendency towards excessive compliance and emphasis on interpersonal dynamics (Graziano & Eisenberg, 1997).

Conscientiousness

Conscientiousness can be described as a form of impulse control that is socially mandated and aids in the facilitation of task and goal-oriented behavior. This includes behaviors such as delaying immediate gratification, conforming to societal norms and rules, as well as engaging in effective planning, organizing, and prioritizing of tasks. Conscientiousness can be characterized by several key attributes, including dependability, accountability, diligence, thinking, accomplishment oriented, and a commitment to adhering to set regulations. The level of an individual's motivation, diligence, persistence, and aspiration for achievement plays a significant role in determining outcomes (Goldberg, 1990). Individuals that exhibit a high level of conscientiousness tend to engage in thoughtful deliberation prior to taking action, while also demonstrating a strong adherence to their moral obligations and feeling of accountability. Moreover, those with a high level of conscientiousness exhibit the tendency to establish well-defined objectives and exert relentless effort in order to attain them, in contrast to individuals with lower levels of conscientiousness. Conscientiousness, a trait encompassing attributes such as accountability, dependability, and deliberateness, has been found to positively influence an individual's inclination to uphold moral principles for both themselves and others (Moon, 2019).

Neuroticism

Positive emotions like worry, apprehension, melancholy, or tension are contrasted with emotional stability and even-temperedness by neuroticism. A person's degree of neuroticism reveals how tense, defensive, insecure, and emotionally volatile they are. As opposed to those with low emotional stability, who are more prone to experience anxiety, sadness, insecurity, and fear, those with strong emotional stability are at ease and confident (Goldberg, 1990). Furthermore, since they lack confidence in their ability to handle the social and task-related risks associated with creative efforts, those who are less emotionally stable avoid circumstances in which they fear they will fail (Raja & Johns, 2004). Emotionally stable individuals are also comfortable and have positive attitudes regarding other people and their work. 2009; Sung & Choi. According to Migliore (2011), emotional stability and calm are accounted for by a low neuroticism score, whereas emotional reactivity to negative emotions like fury and anxiety is accounted for by a high neuroticism score.

Openness

According to the definition provided by Johan and Srivastava (1999), "openness to experience" refers to the extent of an individual's mental and experiential existence in terms of its breadth, depth, originality, and complexity. According to McCrae and Costa's (1992) research, individuals who exhibit openness to new experiences are more inclined to possess qualities such as imagination, unconventionality, autonomy, creativity, and divergent thinking. According to Woodman, Sawyer, and Griffin (1993), individuals in question possess the ability to independently and autonomously make decisions. According to De Hoogh, Hartog, and Koopman (2005), the utilization of these elements has the potential to facilitate the exploration of novel opportunities and innovative strategies for achieving organizational goals by persons who possess a receptive mindset and substantial expertise. Individuals who exhibit high levels of openness to experience tend to possess a wide range of intellectual interests and engage in unconventional thinking, in contrast to individuals with low levels of openness to experience who tend to favor familiarity and have a narrower intellectual focus (Migliore, 2015).

Extraversion

Extraverts, or people with high extraversion scores, derive their energy from social interactions, whereas introverts, or people with low extraversion scores, derive their energy from inside. Extraverts are characterized as gregarious, forceful, like interacting with others, and relish leadership positions. Those who are reserved, formal, serious, silent, prefer working alone, and shy away from leadership roles are characterized as introverts.

(b) Organizational Factors

Human Resource Management Practices

According to Singh and Kassa (2016:644), the term "HRM" refers to a set of policies, processes, and systems that have an impact on the behavior, attitudes, and performance of employees. Human resource management encompasses the comprehensive range of tasks necessary for the recruitment, employment, development, compensation, and administration of personnel within a business.

Human resource practices refer to the particular methods and strategies employed by businesses in the management of their personnel, in accordance with the established human resource policies of the firm (Armstrong, 2011). Conversely, an organization's human resources (HR) policy establishes a set of principles and directives that govern the management of its workforce (Jiang et al., 2012b). This implies that human resources (HR) practices are employed to operationalize the HR policy of the organization, and thus, the selection of HR practices is contingent upon the HR policy embraced by the company (Jiang et al., 2012b). The vast array of human resource practices makes it challenging to comprehensively address all of them within the scope of this particular research (Crawshaw & Hatch, 2014). This study will primarily focus on four key areas of human resource management (HRM) practice, namely employee engagement and empowerment, performance appraisal, remuneration, and reward.

Employee Participation and Empowerment

Currently, there is a growing recognition among organizations regarding the importance of employee participation in the attainment of organizational objectives. Employee engagement provides individuals with the opportunity to assume job responsibilities and engage in collective decision-making processes for the overall well-being of the organization (Management Study Guide, MSG, 2016). Wilkinson et al. (2010, p. 11-12) state that employee participation refers to the various methods employed to engage the employees in decision-making processes across all organizational levels, either through direct involvement or through the representation of their chosen representatives. Individuals at various hierarchical levels perceive themselves as actively participating in decision-making processes, wherein the outcomes of these decisions directly influence their job. Moreover, they recognize the interconnectedness between their work and the overarching objectives of the company. The realization of involvement in decision-making and day-to-day duties is achieved through the implementation of empowerment, team building, and the development of capacities (Denison, Janovics, Young, & Cho, 2006). The concept of empowerment is predicated on the underlying belief that individuals possess the capacity to exercise agency and exert influence over organizational endeavors (Conger & Kanungo, 1988). Empowerment is intricately connected to the notion of process control (Thibaut & Walker, 1975) or voice (Folger, 1977) within the realm of organizational justice theories. The study conducted by Lind et al. (1990) revealed that individuals who were assigned to voice conditions reported significantly greater ratings of procedural justice compared to those who were placed in a no voice experimental condition. Consequently, employees who are empowered and provided with increased opportunity to voice their views are more inclined to perceive procedural fairness compared to their counterparts. Existing research has demonstrated a clear association between organizational justice and empowerment, both in terms of direct and indirect effects. The level of empowerment experienced by individuals in the workplace is positively influenced by the presence of fairness and justice.

Performance Appraisal

The concept of performance appraisal (PA) may appear straightforward, although scholarly research indicates that it is frequently employed as a means of providing performance feedback and evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of individual employees (Ruddin, 2005). According to Jawahar (2007), the effectiveness of assessment systems is likely contingent upon the ratees' views of fairness and their responses to significant elements of the appraisal process. According to Cardy and Dobbins (1994), an appraisal system is likely to be unsuccessful if it is plagued by sentiments of discontent, procedural unfairness, and inequitable evaluations. According to Skarlicki and Folger (1997), the assessment process has the potential to generate significant levels of unhappiness among employees if they perceive the system to be biased, politically motivated, or lacking relevance. According to Holbrook (2002), performance appraisal (PA) plays a crucial role in establishing performance objectives, addressing performance-related challenges, and managing the allocation of awards, disciplinary actions, and terminations.

Compensation and Rewards

The employee incentive system, a crucial aspect of human resources management, has received limited attention in academic research (Gupta & Shaw, 2014), despite its significant role in enhancing individual performance and fostering group cohesion (Cropanzano et al., 2007). The term "it" pertains to a program encompassing a collection of mechanisms that allocate both tangible or financial benefits (such as salary, superannuation, bonus systems, and pension contributions) and intangible or non-financial benefits (such as health and well-being plans, growth and promotion opportunities, career development initiatives, recognition, and favorable work environment conditions). Previous research has indicated a connection between employee reward systems and the four dimensions of organizational justice perceptions (Cole & Flint, 2004, 2005; Laundon et al., 2019). Specifically, employees' perceptions of fairness are associated with their access to distributed benefits (distributive justice), the procedures used to distribute these benefits (procedural justice), the interpersonal relationships between employees and supervisors regarding the received benefits (interpersonal justice), and the information provided about the benefits (informational justice) (Laundon et al., 2019). Hence, the perception of fairness or unfairness in employee benefits can elicit either favorable or negative impacts on their behavior and other organizational results, including productivity and performance. The successful management of employee reward systems presents a promising avenue for enhancing human resources management. By considering

employees' perceptions of benefits, organizations can strive to achieve improved employee effectiveness, retention, and attractiveness (Cole & Flint, 2005).

7.4 Employee Attitudes

(a) Leaders Member Exchange Relationship

The theory of Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) is a leadership theory that focuses on the relationship between leaders and their followers, emphasizing the dyadic nature of this relationship. The LMX hypothesis provides an explanation for the intricate nature of leader-subordinate interactions, wherein leaders establish varying degrees of involvement with their subordinates (Graen and Uhl-Bien, 1995). The subsequent advancement of LMX theory encompasses a depiction of the leader-subordinate relationship through a "life cycle model" consisting of three distinct stages (Graen and Scandura, 1987; Graen and Uhl-Bien, 1991). The connection commences with the initial phase of assessment, during which leaders and subordinates examine one another's intentions, attitudes, and prospective resources to be exchanged, as well as establish expectations for a joint function. During the subsequent phase, the trade arrangements undergo enhancements, leading to the cultivation of mutual trust, loyalty, and respect. Ultimately, during the third phase, the process of exchange transitions from a self-interested perspective to one of mutual commitment.

The theory known as LMX, or Leader-Member Exchange theory, is sometimes referred to as "the vertical dyad linkage theory." This nomenclature is derived from its emphasis on a reciprocal interaction between two individuals, wherein one person has a position of hierarchical power over the other (Yukl, 2010). The establishment and development of these connections are a product of the negotiation process that occurs over a period of time, influenced by the expectations and fulfillment of roles between the leader and their followers (Atitumpong & Badir, 2017). The LMX theory places significant emphasis on the examination of the interaction between leaders and subordinates, going beyond the examination of leaders' or subordinates' qualities, style, or actions (Martin et al., 2017). Within this particular context, supervisors assume the responsibility of overseeing and directing subordinates, operating within a range of different circumstances that ultimately shape the dyadic connection between them. The notion of Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) has gained significant importance in the current body of literature. This theory recognizes the value of relationships and the psychological adjustment of employees, rather than only emphasizing financial incentives (Bernerth et al., 2016; Breevaart et al., 2015). The LMX idea emphasizes the qualitative factors that play a crucial role in individual performance, which are influenced by the interactions between leaders and subordinates (Little et al., 2016). Research on Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) theory consistently demonstrates that leaders engage in differentiation among their subordinates. This differentiation is not arbitrary, since subordinates who are part of the leader's in-group tend to display higher levels of citizenship behavior and report more satisfaction with their superiors (Robbins & Judge, 2015). In contrast, the diverse range of LMX quality gives rise to fluctuations in the relationships between leaders and subordinates, resulting in certain perceptual limitations for employees and therefore impacting their job performance (Tse & Troth, 2013).

(b) Perceived Organizational Support

The notion of perceived organizational support (POS) is grounded in the social exchange theory, which posits that employees offer their effort and loyalty in exchange for the tangible resources and social benefits provided by the company (Blau, 1964). Perceived organizational support (POS) refers to the extent to which employees perceive that their organization values and supports their well-being and professional development. Employees who possess greater levels of perceived organizational support (POS) are likely to have encountered several good social interactions that have contributed to the development of trust. In addition, it has been found that individuals who possess higher levels of perceived organizational support (POS) exhibit more commitment to the firm and its objectives (Kurtessis et al., 2017). The present study investigates the relationship between trust, access to information, and access to opportunity for learning and development as factors influencing perceived organizational support.

7.5 Employee Behaviors

(a) The In-Role Behaviors

Role theory, a prominent theory in social psychology, serves as a theoretical framework for elucidating the variations and consistencies in individual behavior. The fundamental principle underlying role theory is the concept of the role. The term "in-role behavior" is synonymous with "core-task behavior." The initial proposal of this notion was publicly put forth by Katz and Kahn in 1978. The individuals held the belief that in-role behavior constituted a specific type of behavior that was delineated and characterized as a component of employees' job responsibilities, and was also taken into account in the formal remuneration structure inside the firm. According to Williams and Anderson (1991), in-role conduct can be described as encompassing all the necessary behaviors required for the successful performance of one's assigned work responsibilities. The criteria employed for assessing employee performance in terms of in-role behaviors are typically categorized into four groups: rating, quality evaluation, quantity standard, and document data record. Examples of the latter include records pertaining to work safety, absence, and work delays, among others.

(b)Organizational Citizenship Behaviors (OCB)

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) refers to discretionary actions performed by individuals inside an organization that are not explicitly required by their job descriptions, but contribute to the overall functioning and effectiveness of the organization. These behaviors the introduction of the phrase "Organizational Citizenship Behavior" by Dennis Organ and his colleagues three decades ago was influenced by Chester Bernard's (1938) concept of "willingness to cooperate" (Bateman & Organ, 1983; Smith et al., 1983). According to Organ (1988), organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) can be described as actions that are not explicitly acknowledged or rewarded through formal means. Individuals engage in these actions on a voluntary basis, as they are not obligatory but rather contingent upon personal judgment.

According to Hodson (2002), the concept of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) refers to proactive actions taken by individuals to enhance workplace efficiency and integrity, surpassing their prescribed job responsibilities and organizational tasks. According to Robbins and Judge (2007), organizational citizenship conduct refers to discretionary activity exhibited by employees that is not explicitly outlined in their work requirements. This behavior is believed to enhance organizational success and serve the interests of the beneficiaries. Citizenship behavior plays a crucial role in enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of organizations by facilitating resource development, fostering innovation, and promoting adaptation.

Organ (1988) identified five dimensions of OCB that are;

1. Altruistic behaviors, such as providing assistance to new colleagues and willingly dedicating time to others, are commonly aimed towards individuals. However, these acts of altruism also have a positive impact on group efficiency by improving the performance of people.
2. Conscientiousness, characterized by the effective utilization of time and beyond minimal expectations, contributes to the enhanced efficiency of both individuals and groups.
3. The presence of sportsmanship, characterized by the avoidance of complaints and whining, enhances the allocation of time towards productive pursuits inside the business.
4. The practice of demonstrating politeness and consideration, such as providing advance alerts, reminders, and effectively communicating relevant information, serves to enhance and enable the productive utilization of time.
5. Civic virtue, exemplified through engaging in committee service and willingly participating in organizational events, serves to advance the interests of the organization.

7.6 Relationship Between Antecedents of Organizational Justice, Organizational Justice

Over the years, researchers have devoted a great deal of time and attention to establishing and examining the linkage between organizational justices and employee behaviors in different industries. Based on the evidence and findings, it is becoming increasingly clear that organizational justice is an important component that can impact on organizational effectiveness leading to improved behaviors.

The Relationship Between Organizational Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

The association between overall fairness and corporate citizenship behavior is substantiated by empirical study conducted by Greenberg (1993), Niehoff and Moorman (1993), and Williams, Pitre, and Zainuba (2002). Moreover, prior research has consistently demonstrated that procedural fairness is a determinant of organizational citizenship behaviors (Iqbal et al., 2012; Walumbwa, Hartnell & Oke, 2010). When employees perceive the allocation mechanisms for organizational results as fair and just, it is likely to result in their satisfaction and increased likelihood of engaging in organizational citizenship activity. In their study, Walumbwa et al. (2010) discovered a noteworthy correlation between procedural fairness and organizational citizenship practices. In their study, Spector and Che (2014) discovered a positive correlation between distributive justice and organizational citizenship behavior. The assumption of fair treatment is posited to foster social exchange connections characterized by reciprocity, leading to the emergence of obligations on the part of employees to reciprocate towards their supervisors or organizations. Consequently, it is anticipated that corporate citizenship behavior will ensue (Cropanzano et al., 2001). Employees who held the belief that they received fair treatment from their bosses were shown to be considerably more inclined to engage in citizenship practices. The findings of Zhao, Peng, and Chen (2014) align with the notion that employees who perceive support from their superiors are more inclined to engage in citizenship behaviors.

The Relationship Between Personality Traits and Organizational Justice

Previous research has demonstrated a significant correlation between neuroticism and adverse affective states as well as psychological distress (McCrae & Costa, 2003). Additionally, neuroticism has been found to be linked to heightened responsiveness towards instances of unfair treatment (Schmitt, Gollwitzer, Maes, & Arbach, 2005). According to Törnroos et al. (2012), individuals who score high on the neuroticism scale tend to perceive a discrepancy between the benefits they receive and the effort they exert in their workplace. Consequently, these individuals may also perceive a lower level of distributive justice. According to Törnroos et al. (2013), there is a correlation between neuroticism and the experience of reduced decision-making authority. This correlation is also likely to result in a feeling of diminished

procedural justice. Furthermore, it can be inferred that individuals with elevated levels of neuroticism are more susceptible to perceiving the behaviors of others in a negative light (McCrae & Costa, 2003) and may experience reduced levels of social support within the workplace (Lewis, Bates, Posthuma, & Polderman, 2014). Consequently, it is reasonable to assume that they would also perceive a diminished sense of interactional justice in their work environment. Drawing from the available information and prior scholarly investigations, it has been established that neuroticism has a negative correlation with both procedural and interactional justice (Shi et al., 2009). Additionally, neuroticism has been found to be linked to judgments of diminished social fairness throughout the selection process (Truxillo, Bauer, Campion, & Paronto, 2006).

Extraversion has been associated with a number of positive occupational outcomes, including high job satisfaction (Judge et al., 2002), high social support (Lewis et al., 2014), and less work stress (Törnroos et al., 2013). However, there is no evidence linking extraversion to organizational justice (Mayer, Nishii, Schneider, & Goldstein, 2007; Shi et al., 2009; Truxillo et al., 2006). For instance, extraversion was not linked to any of the elements of perceived organizational justice, according to research by Shi et al. (2009), and it was not linked to perceptions of procedural or interactional justice cultures, according to Mayer et al. (2007). This paradox may arise from extraverts' inclination to concentrate on assessments of themselves rather than assessments of their surroundings in relation to others (Truxillo et al., 2006). Furthermore, extraversion is linked to views of greater control, incentives, exertion, and demands (Törnroos et al., 2012, 2013). As a result, they are happy with the result but also believe they had a high input, which suggests they don't think the organizational justice is high or low.

According to prior research, conscientiousness has been linked to perceptions of improved job satisfaction (Judge et al., 2002) and higher equity in efforts made and rewards received (Törnroos et al., 2012). Conscientious people are diligent and persistent (McCrae & Costa, 2003). Conscientiousness traits, however, don't appear to matter when it comes to opinions about organizational justice or fairness (Shi et al., 2009; Truxillo et al., 2006). Therefore, views of success and achievement may value conscientiousness more than perceptions of equity in relation to others.

According to Barrick and Mount (1991), agreeableness people have empathy and trust for other people, and they often feel bad about themselves when they are in a better position than others (Schmitt et al., 2005). As a result, agreeable people are more likely to believe that they are receiving fair treatment and to trust the decisions made inside an organization. As a result, Shi and associates (2009) discovered a relationship between agreeableness and every aspect of organizational fairness. According to earlier studies, agreeableness is linked to the belief that one is receiving appropriate compensation for one's contributions (Törnroos et al., 2012). As a result, pleasant people would perceive greater distributive and procedural justice and would draw favorable social comparisons between input and outcome. Because of their altruistic, helpful, and adaptable attitude, they might also be able to elicit good reactions from others at work (McCrae & Costa, 2003). Because of this, agreeable people may believe that their superiors treat them with more respect, which could lead to a stronger feeling of interactional justice.

Openness is regarded a “double-edged sword” (DeNeve & Cooper, 1998, p. 199) and a trait that, in its broad form, is rarely associated with well-being outcomes (Connelly, Ones, & Chernyshenko, 2014). The characteristics of openness do not translate into feelings or behaviors important in perceiving the environment as threatening or enjoyable. Research on openness and occupational outcomes have to the most part been unsuccessful in finding an association (e.g. Shi et al., 2009; Törnroos et al., 2012).

The Relationship Between Human Resource Management Practices and Organizational Justice

The literature on strategic human resource management (SHRM) has seen an increase in studies focusing on employee perceptions of HR practices. Various theoretical perspectives have been employed in SHRM literature to explore the employee viewpoint on HRM. Consequently, a range of conceptual models have been examined, which consider employee perceptions of HRM as either an antecedent, mediator, or outcome as demonstrated in studies by Beijer et al. (2019) and Wang et al. (2020).

The field of strategic human resource management has experienced an increasing focus on the analysis of employee perspectives of HR practices, as these perceptions significantly influence their effectiveness. The linkages between an organization's human resource practices and the attitudes and actions of its employees are influenced by the views of the employees, as indicated by research conducted by Aryee, Walumbwa, Seidu, and Otaye (2012) and Liao, Toya, Lepak, and Hong (2009). In addition, it has been acknowledged that employee perceptions play a role in influencing the performance of organizational units (Bowen & Ostroff, 2004). The subjective beliefs of employees on the many aspects of human resource management (HRM) inside their respective organizations are reflected in their overall opinions of the HRM practices of their employers (Chang, 2005). Several academic studies and previous scholarly research have been conducted in different developed countries to examine the direct and indirect effects of human resource management (HRM) practices on organizational justice, as noted by Kasemsap (2013:59). The aforementioned research constantly demonstrate a strong association between an organization's human resource management methods and its overall

performance. The subjective perception of employee attitudes towards the human resource management (HRM) practices of employer organizations encompasses several dimensions of HRM inside a company (Chang, 2005).

Organizations rely on policies as a means to mitigate unfairness and provide guidance for decision-making processes (Sitkin & Bies, 1994). However, it is important to note that the mere establishment of regulations does not guarantee employees' acceptance of their fairness. The potential for prejudice among managers in the implementation of policies towards various employees might have detrimental effects on the firm. The justification for developing and executing policies and practices should be provided in order to demonstrate fairness to all employees. According to Greenberg (1987), the presence of unfair treatment results in reduced levels of cooperation among colleagues and a decline in the overall quality of collaboration. According to James and Cropanzano (1994), it is imperative for organizations to establish equitable procedures in areas such as recruitment, performance evaluation, incentive structures, and dispute resolution in order to enhance employees' perception of the business. Prior empirical research (e.g., Dineen et al., 2004; Wooten & Cobb, 1999) has established a correlation between human resource management (HRM) practices and procedural justice. Erdogan, Kraimer, and Liden (2001) conducted a study that revealed a favorable relationship between employees' understanding of performance criteria and appraisal system processes, characterized by objectivity and validity, and their judgments of procedural justice. The perception of fairness and justice in the execution and consequences of HRM practices and processes is crucial for their development (Folger & Cropanzano, 1998).

The Relationship between Organizational Justice and Leader Member Exchange (JS and LME with questions)

The quality of leader-member exchange (LMX) may constitute a significant determinant in shaping individuals' perceptions of fairness. According to Lee (2001), individuals who are part of high-quality leader-member exchange (LMX) relationships tend to receive a greater number of positive rewards compared to their counterparts in low-quality LMX relationships. These rewards include positive performance appraisals, engaging assignments, involvement in decision-making processes, support and attention from leaders, job satisfaction, empowerment, salary/pay, and career advancement opportunities. The perception of distributive justice is heavily influenced by results, with individuals who obtain favorable outcomes being more inclined to view them as fair (Greenberg, 1990; Leventhal, 1980).

Several research have indirectly indicated a potential association between the quality of leader-member exchange (LMX) and the perception of procedural fairness. Stanton (1997) provided evidence suggesting a favorable relationship between trust in the supervisor during performance monitoring and perceptions of procedural fairness. According to Lee (2001), the presence of a high-quality leader-member exchange (LMX) relationship, which is characterized by a strong sense of trust between superiors and subordinates, is likely to result in subordinates seeing a higher level of procedural fairness. According to Lee (2001), the perception of procedural fairness was shown to be greater when employees had access to feedback and input opportunities, as well as when there was sincerity and trustworthiness in the flow of information (e.g., Bies and Shapiro, 1987; Bies, Shapiro, and Cummings, 1988).

The Relationship between Organizational Justice and Perceived Organizational Support

Procedural justice pertains to the interactions an individual has with the established policies and processes inside an organization (Niehoff and Moorman, 1993; Stinglhamber et al., 2006). The concept of procedural justice pertains to an employee's subjective evaluation of the fairness and equity of organizational procedures and rules, as well as their assessment of the level of assistance provided by the company, sometimes referred to as organizational support (POS). Interactional justice is commonly linked to social transactions. The notion of interactional justice holds significant importance within the academic realm, as it has been utilized as a fundamental component in various influential theories, such as Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) theory (Ansari et al., 2007). Typically, senior management is responsible for the development of formal policies and procedures. Positive work behaviors are more likely to be exhibited by workers when they view the procedures and policies to be fair. According to Brockner and Wiesenfeld (1996), when an inventive employee considers procedural justice as equitable, they are more likely to accept a certain level of discrepancy between their perceived input and the rewards they receive. Procedural fairness facilitates an environment that allows inventive personnel to freely exchange ideas with their superiors or colleagues, thereby providing them with the necessary space for creative expression. As previously stated, the concept of perceived organizational support (POS) refers to the extent to which employees think that their organization places value on their contributions and demonstrates concern for their general well-being, hence fulfilling their socio-emotional needs (Eisenberger et al., 1986). This finding further corroborates the notion that procedural justice tends to be linked to elements at the organizational level, while interactional justice tends to be linked to factors at the individual level (Schofield et al., 2006). Similarly, procedural fairness might signify that when an organization provides assistance to its employees, it strengthens the bond between the employees and the company (perceived organizational support, or POS), hence increasing their dedication to the organization's policies, procedures, and objectives.

The Relationship between Leader Member Exchange and Employee Behaviors

The impact of LMX on employees' Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) has also been empirically demonstrated. The study conducted by Cropanzano and Mitchel (2005) revealed a direct relationship between leader-member exchange (LMX) and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB), as explained by the principles of social exchange theory. The concept of social exchange theory, as proposed by Blau in 1964, posits that leader-subordinate relationships that exhibit high-quality exchanges are more likely to result in a strong commitment to organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). This commitment is beneficial for leaders as it facilitates the development of good reciprocal interactions with subordinates who have high-quality leader-member exchanges (LMX), as shown by Organ et al. in 2006. When individuals are driven by the exchange of quality, they feel the need to develop reciprocal relationships through Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). This largely results in employees stating their motives, which are focused on others rather than solely on self-interests (Bowler et al., 2017). Several research have provided evidence supporting the relationship between leader-member exchange (LMX) and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Specifically, these studies have found that employees who have high-quality LMX relationships with their leaders are more likely to engage in OCB (Ilies et al., 2007; Masterson et al., 2000).

Therefore, the LMX's quality has an impact on the levels of delegation, responsibility, and autonomy. Consequently, employees experience a higher degree of latitude, decision influence, and emotions of contribution (Gomez & Rosen, 2001). The aforementioned emotions of contribution may extend beyond the specific duties outlined in employees' job descriptions, and are sometimes referred to as Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). In their study, Liden and Maslyn (1998) created a comprehensive LMX model consisting of four dimensions: contribution, loyalty, affect, and professional respect.

Individuals who possess a lower quality of Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) may experience feelings of envy when making comparisons with their colleagues who have a higher quality of LMX. According to Uhl-Bien and Maslyn (2003), in cases where employees experience dissatisfaction, they may have a reduced inclination to engage in voluntary assistance towards others. According to Harris et al. (2005), individuals who possess a lower quality of leader-member exchange (LMX) are more inclined to exhibit unfavorable responses towards their leaders when performing their job tasks.

The Relationship between Perceived Organizational Support and Employee Behavior

According to the study conducted by Qi et al., (2019), it was observed that employees, upon perceiving organizational support (POS), experience a sense of duty to contribute towards the achievement of the organization's objectives, in line with the exchange norm of reciprocity. According to the social exchange theory, employees who perceive support from their organization are more likely to reciprocate by demonstrating increased effort, loyalty, and willingness to assist colleagues facing challenges. Perceived organizational support (POS) is derived from employees' attributions and evaluations of the organization's treatment towards them (Silva et al., 2022). Consequently, when individuals who get affiliated with an institution perceive themselves as integral to the organization and are held in high regard, employees will develop a sense of obligation to make meaningful contributions to the institution, thereby optimizing organizational performance (Kristiani et al., 2019). According to Bhatti et al. (2019), employees are more likely to engage in Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) when they have a foundation of trust. This is because they have confidence that the organization or their supervisors will provide peer feedback as a result of their efforts.

According to previous research, it has been found that employees who experience support from their organization are more likely to feel a sense of obligation to contribute towards the achievement of organizational goals, as suggested by the reciprocal norm (Thompson et al., 2020). Based on the tenets of the social exchange theory, it may be posited that employees who possess a perception of organizational support are likely to exhibit heightened levels of job effort and display more loyalty towards the business as a reciprocal response (Imran et al., 2020). Hence, employees within an organization who perceive themselves as being regarded as integral members and esteemed by their organization will assume a sense of responsibility in making maximal contributions to their organization, thereby optimizing its performance (Ridwan et al., 2020). Moreover, the psychological process through which employees perceive their organization's loyalty, also known as commitment, is intricately linked to the theoretical framework of social exchange and the psychological contract that exists between employees and their organization (Garcia et al., 2021). According to Shabbir et al. (2021), the perception of organizational support (POS) has the potential to influence employees' work attitudes and behaviors. This influence is mediated through the association between effort and anticipated rewards, as well as the reinforcement of personal social and emotional needs. As a result, organizations have the ability to utilize employees' perception of organizational support (POS) in order to enhance their organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Furthermore, in accordance with the social exchange theory and the reciprocal norm, individuals inside an organization form a broad perception on the degree to which their contributions and overall welfare are valued by the organization. Research conducted by Kurtessis et al. (2017) and Aboramadan et al. (2022) suggests that employees who perceive a trustworthy relationship with their employer are more like to exhibit Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).

7.7 Pervious Related Studies

Butler, Andrea (2012) investigated how employees' willingness to participate in two categories of discretionary behaviors—withdrawal behaviors and organizational citizenship—is influenced by their beliefs of justice about the use of electronic monitoring. The social exchange method was chosen. 208 workers from a call center, a police department, and a municipal administration provided the data. Results showed that employees' desire to participate in organizational citizenship and withdrawal behaviors is influenced by their beliefs of justice in relation to the deployment of electronic monitoring. Additionally, it was discovered that affective commitment, organizational trust, and perceived organizational support acted as mediators in the relationship between citizenship and withdrawal behaviors and perceptions of justice related to the usage of electronic monitoring.

A multifactorial justice social exchange model was tested by Rupp & Cropanzano (2002). The supervisor's and the organization's overall opinions of justice were contrasted in this study. Presenting our model, we postulate that the development of multifoci social exchange relationships acts as a mediating factor in the relationship between multifoci justice and multifoci outcomes (e.g., performance and OCB). This study discovered that the information of multifarious social exchange relationships acts as a mediator in the relationship between multifarious justice and multifarious outcomes (performance and OCB).

In the study conducted by Lee (2000), an investigation was carried out to explore the intermediary function of distributive and procedural justice in establishing a connection between leader-member exchange and several outcome variables, namely work satisfaction, organizational commitment, and turnover intentions. The research was specifically focused on the hotel industry. The evaluation of the model was conducted utilizing the methodology of structural equation modeling (SEM). The findings of the study demonstrated that the concept of distributive justice exerted a direct and beneficial impact on individuals' level of job satisfaction, while also exhibiting a negative association with their plans to leave the organization. The influence of distributive justice on procedural justice was found to be significant. The presence of procedural justice was found to have a significant and beneficial impact on levels of job satisfaction. Nevertheless, there was a negative correlation between procedural justice and organizational commitment, whereas a positive correlation was observed between procedural justice and turnover intentions. Therefore, the impact of distributive justice on workers' work-related outcomes was found to be more significant compared to procedural justice. This study additionally demonstrated actual findings about the influence of interpersonal working relationships on employees' sense of fairness. The views of fairness among employees were positively influenced by the quality of interpersonal working relationships. Hence, it can be concluded that both distributive and procedural justice have a significant moderating effect on the associations between leader-member exchange (LMX) and variables such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, and turnover intentions.

The study conducted by Gichira (2016) aimed to examine the impact of employees' perceptions of organizational justice on their commitment inside Non-Governmental Organizations operating in the health sector in Kenya. The research utilized descriptive and correlational research methodologies, employing a statistical sample of 195 employees who hold major responsibilities in 17 Non-Governmental Organizations. The study's findings indicate that there is a noteworthy correlation between perceptions of distributive justice, procedural justice, interpersonal justice, and informational justice, and affective, continuance, and normative commitment within non-governmental organizations operating in the health sector in Kenya. Nevertheless, it was shown that human resource activities, including socialization, involvement, training, and development, did not have a significant moderating effect on the link between organizational justice and commitment.

In a study conducted by Zhang (2006), the researcher examined the antecedents and effects of organizational justice. The sample consisted of 242 supervisor-subordinate dyads from Chinese firms. The study constructs and evaluates a path model that illustrates the relationship between perceived human resource (HR) practices, including empowerment, psychological contract breach, and communication, and the perception of organizational justice, encompassing distributive, procedural, and interactional justice. Additionally, the model examines the impact of these justice perceptions on organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) and turnover intention. The findings present empirical data regarding the influence of many factors on individuals' perceptions of distributive justice. Specifically, the results demonstrate the effects of empowerment on distributive justice perceptions, the impact of psychological contract breach on both distributive and procedural justice, and the role of communication in shaping perceptions of procedural justice and interactional justice. The findings of this study also indicate that individuals' perceptions of distributive, procedural, and interactional justice have a beneficial impact on their organizational citizenship behavior (OCB). Additionally, it was observed that perceptions of distributive and interactional justice are associated with employees' intention to leave the organization.

In their study, Tarban and Arriffm (2019) examined the role of organizational justice as a mediator in the associations between human resource management practices and organizational commitment among academic staff in Malaysian higher education institutions. A Likert Scale survey questionnaire was utilized to obtain data from 496

respondents across three public colleges in Malaysia. The data analysis was performed utilizing Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approaches through the utilization of AMOS 20. The findings collected revealed robust positive correlations between human resource management methods and organizational justice, as well as between organizational justice and organizational commitment. There exists a discernible and inverse correlation between human resource management techniques and organizational commitment.

In their study, Yang Fu and Zhang Lihua (2012) sought to enhance comprehension regarding the association between perceived organizational support (POS) and organizational justice, namely distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactive justice. Additionally, they aimed to examine the moderating impact of conscientiousness. The data was collected by a field survey conducted on a sample of 520 professional managers employed in two distinct businesses, namely the manufacturing industry and the service industry, inside the country of China. Confirmatory factor analysis and moderated hierarchical analysis were employed to examine hypotheses that had not been previously examined. Based on the findings, it was observed that after accounting for control variables such as age, tenure, education, and position, the influence of organizational justice (specifically distributive justice, procedural justice, and interactive justice) had a favorable impact on POS within the service sample. Additionally, it was found that the interaction between distributive justice and conscientiousness was statistically significant in both the manufacturing and service samples.

7.8 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

The conceptual framework for this study was developed based on the theoretical background and previous studies. Furthermore, the linkages between variables are developed based on literature review on theories and previous studies. As shown in figure, this study will firstly explore possible antecedents of employee's perceptions of Organizational justice. The influence of individual factor of personality and HRM practices are adopted as antecedents of organizational justice was the primary interest of the study. Then it will analyze the relationship between organizational justice and employee behaviors directly and indirectly through mediators and moderators (leader member exchange relationship and organizational support).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Source: own compilation

8. ORGANIZATION OF THE STUDY

The contents of the study are organized in five chapters. In chapter one, the brief introduction about the research problem, rationale of the study, objective of the study, methods of the study, scope and limitations of the study, and organization of the study are presented. Chapter two is the literature review section of the study. It includes the detail theoretical background of organizational justice, perception of justice and social exchange theory, employee attitudes, employee behaviors, conceptual framework of the study. Chapter three presents the research methodology of the study that consists of research area, sampling and data collection, questionnaire, measurement of the variables used in this research, analytical methods and profile of the respondents. Chapter four presents analysis on organizational justice and employee behaviors at hotels in Myanmar. The last chapter, chapter five presents' findings and discussions of the study, suggestions and recommendations, contributions of the study and needs for further studies.

9. REFERENCES

1. Tse, H. H. M., Lam, C. K., Lawrence, S. A., & Huang, X. (2013). When my supervisor dislikes you more than me: The effect of dissimilarity in leader-member exchange on coworkers' interpersonal emotion and perceived help. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 98, 974-988.
2. Lambe C.J., Wittmann C.M., Spekman R.E. Social Exchange Theory and Research on Business-to-Business Relational Exchange. *J. Bus. Bus. Mark.* 2001; 8:1–36. doi: 10.1300/J033v08n03_01. [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
3. Adams, J. S. (1965). Inequity in social exchange. In L. Berkowitz (Ed.), *Advances in experimental social psychology* (Vol. 2), New York: Academic Press, 267-299
4. Ali, S. H. B (2016) The impact of organizational justice on employee intrinsic and extrinsic performance: A case study in Kota Kin Abalu Polytechnic, Malaysia. *Kuwait Chapter of Arabian Journal of Business Management Review* 5 (11), 1 -12.
5. Ansari, M.A., Kee Mui Hung, D. and Aafaqi, R. (2007), "Leader-member exchange and attitudinal outcomes: role of procedural justice climate", *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, Vol. 28 No. 8, pp. 690-709.
6. Armstrong, M. (2011). *Armstrong's handbook of strategic human resource management*, London: Kogan Page.
7. Aryee, S., Walumbwa, F. O., Seidu, E. Y., & Otaye, L. E. (2012). Impact of high-performance work systems on individual-and branch-level performance: Test of a multilevel model of intermediate linkages. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 97(2), 287–300. doi:10.1037/a0028116
8. Atitumpong, A. and Badir, Y.F. (2017) "Leader-member exchange, learning orientation and innovative work behavior", *Journal of Workplace Learning*, 30(1), pp. 32-47.
9. Barnard, C. (1938). *The Functions of the Executive*. Cambridge: Harvard University.
10. Barrick, M. R., & Mount, M. K. (1991). The Big 5 personality dimensions and job-performance - a metaanalysis. *Personnel Psychology*, 44(1), 1–26. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744.6570.1991.tb00688.x>
11. Barsky, A., & Kaplan, S. A. (2007). If you feel bad, it's unfair: a quantitative synthesis of affect and organizational justice perceptions. *The Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(1), 286–95. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.92.1.286>
12. Bateman, T. S., & Organ, D. W. (1983). Job satisfaction and the good soldier: The relationship between affect and employee "citizenship". *Academy of Management Journal*, 26(4), 587-595.
13. Beijer, S., Peccei, R., Van Veldhoven, M., & Paauwe, J. (2019). The turn to employees in the measurement of human resource practices: A critical review and proposed way forward. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 1, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1748-8583.12229>
14. Bernerth, J. B. and Hirschfeld, R. R. (2016) "The subjective well-being of group leaders as explained by the quality of leader-member exchange", *Leadership Quarterly*, 27(4), pp. 697–710.
15. Bies, R. J., & Moag, J. F. (1986). Interactional justice: Communication criteria of fairness. In R. J. Lewicki, B. H. Sheppard, & M. H. Bazerman (Eds.). *Research on Negotiations in Organizations*, 1, 43-55.
16. Bies, R.J., and Shapiro, D.L. 1987. Interactional fairness judgments: The influence of causal accounts, *Social Justice Research* 1, 199-218.
17. Bies, R.J.; Shapiro, D.L.; and Cummings, L.L. 1988. Causal accounts and managing conflict: Is it enough to say it's my fault? *Communication Research* 15, 381-399.
18. Blau P.M. *Exchange and Power in Social Life*. Transaction Publishers; Piscataway, NJ, USA: 1964. [Google Scholar]
19. Blau, P. M. (1964) *Exchange and power in social life*. New York: Wiley.
20. Bowen, D. E., & Ostroff, C. (2004). Understanding HRM-firm performance linkages: The role of the "strength" of the HRM system. *Academy of Management Review*, 29, 203–221. doi:10.5465/amr.2004.12736076
21. Bowler, W. M., Paul, J. B. and Halbesleben, J. R. B. (2017) "Lmx and attributions of organizational citizenship behavior motives: When is citizenship perceived as brownnosing?", *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 34(3), pp. 139-152.
22. Breevaart, K., Bakker, A. B., Demerouti, E. and Van Den Heuvel, M. (2015) "Leader-member exchange, work engagement, and job performance", *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 30(7), pp. 754–770.
23. Brockner, J. and Wiesenfeld, B.M. (1996), "An integrative framework for explaining reactions to decisions: interactive effects of outcomes and procedures", *Psychological Bulletin*, Vol. 120 No. 2, pp. 189-208.

24. Butler, A. (2012). The effects of organizational justice perceptions associated with the use of electronic monitoring on employees' organizational citizenship and withdrawal behaviours: A social exchange perspective.
25. Butler, Andrea, "The Effects of Organizational Justice Perceptions Associated with the use of Electronic Monitoring on Employees' Organizational Citizenship and Withdrawal Behaviors: A Social Exchange Perspective" (2012). Electronic Theses and Dissertations. 478. <https://scholar.uwindsor.ca/etd/478>
26. Cardy, R.L. and Dobbins, G.H. (1994), *Performance Appraisal: Alternative Perspectives*, South-Western Publishing Company, Cincinnati, OH, p. 54.
27. Chang, E. (2005). Employees' overall perception of HR effectiveness. *Human Relations*, 58(4), 523 – 544. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0018726705055037>
28. Cohen-Charash, Y., & Spector, P. E. (2001). The role of justice in organizations: A meta-analysis. *Organizational Behaviour and Human Decision Processes*, 86, 2,278-321.
29. Cole, N. D., & Flint, D. H. (2004). Perceptions of distributive and procedural justice in employee benefits: Flexible versus traditional benefit plans. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 19(1), 19–40. <https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940410520646>
30. Cole, N. D., & Flint, D. H. (2005). Opportunity Knocks: Perceptions of Fairness in Employee Benefits. *Compensation & Benefits Review*, 37(2), 55–62. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886368704274446>
31. Colquitt, J. A. (2001). On the dimensionality of organizational justice: a construct validation of a measure. *Journal of applied psychology*, 86(3), 386-400.
32. Colquitt, J. A., & J. M. Chertkoff. (2000). Explaining Injustice: The Interactive Effect of Explanation and Outcome on Fairness Perceptions and Task Motivation. *Journal of Management*, 28(5), 591-610
33. Colquitt, J. A., Scott, B. A., Rodell, J. B., Long, D. M., Zapata, C. P., Conlon, D. E., & Wesson, M. J. (2013). Justice at the millennium, a decade later: a meta-analytic test of social exchange and affect-based perspectives. *The Journal of Applied Psychology*, 98(2), 199–236. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0031757>
34. Conger, J. A., & Kanungo, R. N. (1988). The empowerment process: Integrating theory and practice. *Academy of Management Review*, 13, 471-482.
35. Costa Jr, P. T., & McCrae, R. R. (1992). Four ways five factors are basic. *Personality and individual differences*, 13(6), 653-665.
36. Costello, S.J. (1994), *Managing Change at Work*, Irwin Professional Pub, New York, NY.
37. Crawshaw, J.R. & Hatch, A. (2014). Introduction: Context and challenges for HRM. In J. R. Crawshaw, P. Budhwar, & A. Davis, eds. *Human resource management: Strategic & international perspectives*. London: SAGE, pp. 2–25.
38. Cropanzano R., Mitchell M.S. Social Exchange Theory: An Interdisciplinary Review. *J. Manag.* 2005; 31:874–900. doi: 10.1177/0149206305279602. [CrossRef] [Google Scholar]
39. Cropanzano, Russell, & Stein, J. H. (2009). Organizational Justice and Behavioral Ethics: Promises and Prospects. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 19(2), 193 233. <https://doi.org/10.5840/beq200919211>
40. Cropanzano, R. and Mitchell, M. (2005) "Social exchange theory: An interdisciplinary review", *Journal of Management*, 31(6), pp. 874-900.
41. De Hoogh, A. H., Den Hartog, D. N., & Koopman, P. L. (2005). Linking the Big Five-Factors of personality to charismatic and transactional leadership; perceived dynamic work environment as a moderator. *Journal of Organizational Behavior: The International Journal of Industrial, Occupational and Organizational Psychology and Behavior*, 26(7), 839-865.
42. Demirel, Yavuz., Iman Elhusadi, & Aza Alhasadi, (2018). The Relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Organizational Factors. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI)*, 7(3), 27-39.
43. Denison, D. R., Janovics, J., Young, J., & Cho, H. J. (2006). Diagnosing organizational cultures: Validating a model and method. Documento de trabajo. Denison Consulting Group
44. Dineen, B. R, Noe, RA., & Wang, C. (2004). Perceived fairness of web-based applicant screening procedures: Weighing the rules of justice and individual differences. *Human Resource Management*, 43, 127-145.
45. Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchison, S. and Sowa, D. (1986), "Perceived organizational support", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 71 No. 1, pp. 500-507.
46. Eisenberger, R., Huntington, R., Hutchison, S., and Sowa, D. (1986). Perceived organizational support. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 71, 500–507. doi: 10.1037/0021-9010.71.3.500
47. Endrogan, B., Kraimer, M.L. & Liden R.C. (2001). Procedural justice as a two-dimensional construct :An examination in the performance appraisal context .*Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 37, 205-222.
48. Folger, R. G. & Cropanzano, R. (1998). *Organizational justice and human resource management*, Sage
49. Folger, R., & Cropanzano, R. (1998). *Organizational justice and human resource management*. CA: Thous and Oaks.
50. Frenkel, S. J., & Bednall, T. (2016). How training and promotion opportunities, career expectations, and two dimensions of organizational justice explain discretionary work effort. *Human Performance*, 29(1), 16–32. doi:10.1080/08959285.2015.1120306

51. Garcia, P. R. J. M., Amarnani, R. K., Bordia, P., and Restubog, S. L. D. (2021). When support is unwanted: The role of psychological contract type and perceived organizational support in predicting bridge employment intentions. *J. Vocat. Behav.* 125:103525. doi: 10.1016/j.jvb.2020.103525
52. George. J. M & Jones G. R (2006). *Contemporary Management*. Boston, McGraw Hill.
53. Gichira, P. M. (2016). Influence of Organizational Justice on Commitment of Employees in Health Sector Non-Governmental organizations in Kenya.
54. Goldberg, L. R. (1990). The development of markers for the Big-Five factor structure. *Psychological assessment*, 4(1), 26.
55. Gomez, C., & Rosen, B. (2001). The leader-member exchange as a link between managerial trust and employee empowerment. *Group and Organization Management*, 26, 53-69.
56. Graen, G. B. and Scandura, T. (1987) "Toward a psychology of dyadic organizing", *Research in Organizational Behavior*, 9, pp. 175-208.
57. Graen, G. B. and Uhl-Bien, M. (1991) "The transformation of work group professionals into self-managing and partially self-designing contributors: Toward a theory of leadership-making", *Journal of Management System*, 3(3), pp. 33-48.
58. Graen, G. B. and Uhl-Bien, M. (1995) "Development of leader-member exchange (LMX) theory of leadership over 25 years: applying a multi-level multi-domain perspective", *Leadership Quarterly*, 6, pp. 219-247.
59. Graen, G. B., and Scandura, T. A. (1987). Toward a psychology of dyadic organizing. *Res. Organ. Behav.* 9, 175-208.
60. Graham, J. W. (1989). Organizational citizenship behavior: Construct redefinition, operationalization, and validation. Unpublished working paper, Loyola University of Chicago, Chicago, IL, 68.
61. Graziano, W. G., & Eisenberg, N. (1997). Agreeableness: A dimension of personality. In *Handbook of personality psychology* (pp. 795-824). Academic Press.
62. Greenberg, J. (1987). A taxonomy of organizational justice theories. *Academy of Management review*, 12, 9-22.
63. Greenberg, J. (1990a). Organizational justice: Yesterday, today, and tomorrow. *Journal of Management*, 16 ,(2), 399-432.
64. Greenberg, J. (1993). The social side of fairness: Interpersonal and informational classes of organizational justice. In R. Cropanzano (Ed.), *Justice in the workplace: Approaching fairness in human resource management* (pp.79 103). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
65. Greenberg, J. (2001). Setting the justice agenda: seven unanswered questions about "what, why, and how." *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 58(2), 210-219. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.2001.1792>
66. Greenberg, J. 1990a. Looking fair vs. being fair: Managing impressions of organizational justice, *Research in Organizational Behavior* 12, 111-157
67. Greenberg, J., & Colquitt, J. A. (Eds.). (2013). *Handbook of organizational justice*. Psychology Press. Mahwah, New Jersey: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
68. Gupta, N., & Shaw, J. D. (2014). Employee compensation: The neglected area of HRM research. *Human Resource Management Review*, 24(1), 1-4. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hrmr.2013.08.007>
69. Ha, J. P., & Ha, J. (2015). Organizational justice-affective commitment relationship in a team sport setting: The moderating effect of group cohesion. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 21(01), 107-124. doi:10.1017/jmo.2014.67
70. Haiy An Zhang,B.M.(2006).Antecedents And Consequences of Organizational Justice :An Investigation in China.
71. Hassan, A. (2002). Organizational justice as a determinant of organizational commitment and intention to leave. *Asian Academy of Management Journal*, 7(2), 55-66.
72. Hayat Bhatti, M., Ju, Y., Akram, U., Hasnat Bhatti, M., Akram, Z., and Bilal, M. (2019). Impact of participative leadership on organizational citizenship behavior: Mediating role of trust and moderating role of continuance commitment: Evidence from the Pakistan hotel industry. *Sustainability* 11:1170. doi: 10.3390/su11041170
73. Hodson, R., (2002), Management citizenship behavior and its consequence, *Work and Occupations*.vol.29 (1), 64-96.
74. Holbrook, R.L. (2002), "Contact points and flash points: conceptualizing the use of justice mechanisms in the performance appraisal interview", *Human Resource Management Review*, Vol. 12 No. 1, pp. 101-23.
75. Hurtz, G. M., & Donovan, J. J. (2000). Personality and job performance: The big five revisited. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 85(6), 869-879. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0021-9010.85.6.869>
76. Ibrahim, M. E., Al Sejini, S., & Al Qassimi, O. A. (2004). Job satisfaction and performance of government employees in UAE. *Journal of Management Research*, 4(1), 1-11.
77. Ilies, R., Nahrgang, J. D. and Morgeson, F. (2007) "Leader-member exchange and citizenship behaviors: A meta analysis", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 92(1), pp. 269-77.
78. Iqbal, K. (2013). Determinants of Organizational Justice and Its Impact on Job Satisfaction. *A Pakistan Base Survey. Internasional Review of Management and Busines Research*, 2 (1), 48-56.
79. James, K., & Cropanzano, R. (1994). Dispositional group loyalty and individual action for the benefit of an ingroup: Experimental and correlational evidence. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 60, 179 205.

80. Jawahar, I. M. (2002). A model of organizational justice and workplace aggression. *Journal of management*, 28(6), 811-834.
81. Jawahar, I.M. (2007), "The influence of perceptions of fairness on performance appraisal reactions", *Journal of Labor Research*, Vol. 28 No. 4, pp. 735-54.
82. Jiang, K., Lepak, D.P., Han, K., Hong, Y., Kim, A. & Winkler, A.L. (2012b). Clarifying the construct of human resource systems: Relating human resource management to employee performance. *Human Resource Management Review*, 22(2), pp.73–85.
83. Judge, T. A., & Ilies, R. (2002). Relationship of personality to performance motivation: a meta analytic review. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(4), 797–807. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0021-9010.87.4.797>
84. Judge, T. A., Heller, D., & Mount, M. K. (2002). Five-factor model of personality and job satisfaction: a meta-analysis. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 87(3), 530–541. <https://doi.org/10.1037//0021-9010.87.3.530>
85. Kalay, F (2016) The impact of organizational justice on employee performance: A survey in Turkey and Turkish context. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies* 6 (1), 1 21.
86. Kasemsap, K. (2013). Innovative Human Resource Practices: A functional framework and causal model of organizational rewards, organizational justice, perceived organizational support and job satisfaction. Faculty of Management Sciences, Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University, Bangkok, Thailand, 65(12), 57-61.
87. Katz, D., & Kahn, R. L. (1978). *The social psychology of organizations* (Vol. 2). New York: Wiley.
88. Kehoe, R. R., & Wright, P. M. (2013). The impact of high-performance human resource practices on employees' attitudes and behaviors. *Journal of Management*, 39(2), 366-391. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/0149206310365901>
89. Konowsky, M. A. (2000). Understanding Procedural Justice and Its Impact on Business Organizations, *Journal of Management*, 26(3), 489-511
90. Kristiani, W., Matin, M., and Sugiarto, S. (2019). The effect of organizational culture and perceived organizational support (POS) towards organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) Teacher SDK PENABUR Jakarta. *Int. J. Educ. Vocat. Stud.* 1, 528–532. doi: 10.29103/ijevs.v1i6.1680
91. Kurtessis, J.N., Eisenberger, R., Ford, M.T., Buffardi, L.C., Stewart, K.A. and Adis, C.S. (2017), "Perceived organizational support: a meta-analytic evaluation of organizational support theory", *Journal of Management*, Vol. 43 No. 6, pp. 1854-1884, doi: 10.1177/0149206315575554
92. Laundon, M., Cathcart, A., & McDonald, P. (2019). Just benefits? Employee benefits and organisational justice. *Employee Relations*, 41(4), 708–723. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/ER-11-2017-0285/full/html>
93. Lee, H.-R. "An Empirical Study of Organizational Justice as a Mediator of the Relationships among Leader-Member Exchange and Job Satisfaction, Organizational Commitment, and Turnover Intentions in the Lodging Industry" (2000).
94. Lee, K., and Duffy, M. K. (2019). A functional model of workplace envy and job performance: when do employees capitalize on envy by learning from envied targets? *Acad. Manag. J.* 62, 1085–1110. doi: 10.5465/amj.2016.1202
95. Leventhal, G.S. 1980. What should be done with equity theory? In K.J. Gergen, M.S. Greenberg, and R.H. Willis (eds.), *Social Exchange: Advances in Theory and Research*, New York: Plenum.
96. Liao, H., Toya, K., Lepak, D. P., & Hong, Y. (2009). Do They See Eye to Eye? Management and employee perspectives of high-performance work systems and influence processes on service quality. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 94(2), 371–391. doi: 10.1037/a0013504
97. Liden, R. C., & Maslyn, J. M. (1998). Multidimensionality of leader-member exchange: An empirical assessment through scale development. *Journal of Management*, 24, 43-72.
98. Lind, E. A., Kanfer, R., & Earley, P. C. (1990). Voice, control, and procedural justice: Instrumental and non-instrumental concerns in fairness judgments. *Journal of Personality & Social Psychology*, 59, 952-959.
99. Little, L. M., Gooty, J. and Williams, M. (2016) "The role of leader emotion management in leader-member exchange and follower outcomes", *Leadership Quarterly*, 27(1), pp. 85–97.
100. Lopez-Cabrales, A., Valle, R., & Herrero, I. (2006). The contribution of core employees to organizational capabilities and efficiency. *Human Resource Management*, 45(1), 127–145. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm>
101. M.S.G, Management Study Guide (2016). Advantages of Participative Management. Retrieved from: <https://www.managementstudyguide.com/participative-management-advantages-disadvantages.htm>.
102. Mahendra, I. dan Ida B. Ketut Surya. (2017). Pengaruh Iklim Organisasi, Motivasi Kerja dan Keadilan Organisasi terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). *E-Jurnal Manajemen Universitas Udayana*, 6(9), 4569-4688.
103. Martin, R., Thomas, G., Legood, A. and Dello Russo, S. (2017) "Leader-member exchange (LMX) differentiation and work outcomes: Conceptual clarification and critical review", *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 39(2), pp. 151–168.
104. Masterson S. S., Lewis, K., Goldman, B. M. and Taylor, M. S. (2000) "Integrating justice and social exchange: The differing effects of fair procedures and treatment on work relationships", *Academy of Management Journal*, 43, pp. 738–748.
105. McCrae, R. R., & Costa, P. T. (2003). *Personality in adulthood: emerging lives enduring dispositions*. New York: Guilford press.

106. Migliore, G (2015). Are farmers in alternative food networks social entrepreneurs? Evidence from a behavioral approach. *Journal of Agricultural and Environmental Ethics*, 28(5), 885-902.
107. Migliore, G. (2016). Is there sustainable entrepreneurship in the wine industry? Exploring Sicilian wineries participating in the SOStain program. *Wine Economics and Policy*, 5(1), 14-23.
108. Moorman, R. H., & Blakely, G. L. (1995). Individualism-collectivism as an individual difference predictor of organizational citizenship behavior. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 16(2), 127-142.
109. Moorman, R. H., Blakely, G. L., & Niehoff, B. P. (1998). Does perceived organizational support mediate the relationship between procedural justice and organizational citizenship behavior? *Academy of Management Journal*, 41(3), 351-357.
110. Mustafa, Dermirkiran., Taskaya Serap, & Dinc Mehmet, (2016). A study on the relationship between organizational justice and organizational citizenship behavior in hospitals. *International Journal of Business Management and Economic Research*, 7 (2), 547-554
111. Niehoff, B.P. and Moorman, R.H. (1993), "Justice as a mediator of the relationship between methods of monitoring and organizational citizenship behavior", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 36 No. 3, pp. 527-556.
112. Okocha, B. F., & Anyanwu, S.A.C. (2016). Organizational justice and employee satisfaction: A study of selected Banks in Port Harcourt. *International Journal of Advanced Academic Research Social & Management Sciences*, 2(9), 62-74.
113. Organ, D. W. (1988). *Organizational citizenship behavior: The good soldier syndrome*. Lexington Books/DC Heath and Com.
114. Organ, D. W., Podsakoff, P. M. and MacKenzie, S. B. (2006) *Organizational Citizenship Behavior: Its Nature, Antecedents, and Consequences*, Beverly Hills, CA: Sage
115. Paramita, Patricia Dhiana. (2012). Organizational Citizenship Behaviour (OCB): Aspek Dari Aktivitas Individual Dalam Bekerja, 10 (24), 1412-8489.
116. Patterson, F. (2001). Developments in work psychology: Emerging issues and future trends Fiona. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 74(4), 381–390.
117. Qi, L., Liu, B., Wei, X., and Hu, Y. (2019). Impact of inclusive leadership on employee innovative behavior: Perceived organizational support as a mediator. *PLoS One* 14: e0212091. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0212091
118. Rai, S. (2015). Organizational justice and employee mental health's moderating roles in organizational identification. *South Asian Journal of Global Business Research*, 4(1), 68-84. doi:10.1108/SAJGBR-01-2014-0006
119. Ridwan, M., Mulyani, S. R., and Ali, H. (2020). Improving employee performance through perceived organizational support, organizational commitment and organizational citizenship behavior. *Syst. Rev. Pharm.* 11, 839–849.
120. Robbins, S. P. and Judge, T. A. (2015) *Organisational Behaviour* (16th ed), New Jersey: Pearson Education, Inc.
121. Robbins, S.P & Judge, T.A, (2007). Psychological contracts and OCB. *Journal of Organizational behavior* vol.25 (5).
122. Roohi, M and M. Feizi. (2013). Organizational Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior in Islamic Azad University. *International Journal of Management research and Review*, 3(3), 2513-2521.
123. Ruddin, Z. Z. (2005). Employees' perception on the effectiveness of performance appraisal system. Unpublished Master of Business Administration thesis. Open University Malaysia.
124. Rupp, D. E., & Cropanzano, R. (2002). The mediating effects of social exchange relationships in predicting workplace outcomes from multifoci organizational justice. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 89(1), 925-946.
125. Saifi, Imran Akbar and Khuram Shahzad. (2017). The Mediating Role of job Satisfaction in the Relationship between Organizational Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*, 11(1), 125-145.
126. Saifi, Imran Akbar and Khuram Shahzad. (2017). The Mediating Role of job Satisfaction in the Relationship between Organizational Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*, 11(1), 125-145.
127. Schofield, D., Page, S., Lyle, D. and Walker, T. (2006), "Ageing of the baby boomer generation: how demographic change will impact on city and rural GP and nursing workforce", *Rural and Remote Health*, Vol. 6 No. 4, pp. 1-9.
128. Shabbir, T., Naz, K., and Trivedi, S. D. (2021). Perceived organizational support and employee performance. *Int. J. Educ. Adm. Manag. Leadersh.* 2, 35–44. doi: 10.51629/ijeamal.v2i1.14
129. Shan, S., Ishaq, H. M., & Shaheen, M. A. (2015). Impact of organizational justice on job performance in libraries: Mediating role of leader-member exchange relationship. *Library Management*, 36(1/2), 70–85. doi:10.1108/LM-01-2014-0003
130. Shapiro, D. L., Buttner, E. H., & Barry, B. (1994). Explanations: What factors enhance their perceived adequacy? *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 58(3), 346 – 368. <https://doi.org/10.1006/obhd.1994.1041>
131. Silva, R., Dias, Á, Pereira, L., da Costa, R. L., and Gonçalves, R. (2022). Exploring the direct and indirect influence of perceived organizational support on affective organizational commitment. *Soc. Sci.* 11:406. doi: 10.3390/socsci11090406

132. Singh, N. R., & Kassa, B. (2016). The impact of human resource management practice on organizational performance - A Study on Debre Brehan University International. *Journal of Recent Advances in Organizational Behaviour and Decision Sciences*, 1(1), 643-662.
133. Sitkin, S., & Bies, R. (1994). The Legalistic organization. *Organization Science*, 4(3), 345-351.
134. Skarlicki, D. P., & Latham, G. P. (1997). Leadership training in organizational justice to increase citizenship behavior within a labor union: A replication. *Personnel Psychology*, 50(3), 617-633.
135. Skarlicki, D.P. and Folger, R. (1997), "Retaliation in the workplace: the roles of distributive, procedural and interactional justice", *Journal of Applied Psychology*, Vol. 82 No. 3, pp. 434-43.
136. Spreitzer, G.M. (1995), "Psychological empowerment in the workplace: dimensions, measurement, and validation", *Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 38 No. 5, pp. 1442-1465.
137. Stanton, J.M. 1997. Performance monitoring and fairness perceptions: Characteristics, context, and correlates, University of Connecticut: Unpublished doctoral dissertation.
138. Stinglhamber, F., De Cremer, D. and Mercken, L. (2006), "Perceived support as a mediator of the relationship between justice and trust a multiple foci approach", *Group & Organization Management*, Vol. 31 No. 4, pp. 442-468.
139. Sung, S. H., & Choi, J. (2009). Responsible entrepreneurship, nation brand, and public policy. *Korea Observer*, 40(2), 369.
140. Tarban and Arriffm (2019). Investigating the impact of human resource management practices on organizational justice and organizational commitment among academic staff of public universities in Malaysia. *Academic Research International* Vol. 10(2) June 2019.
141. Thibaut, J., & Walker, L. (1975). *Procedural justice: A psychological analysis*. Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
142. Thompson, P. S., Bergeron, D. M., and Bolino, M. C. (2020). No obligation? How gender influences the relationship between perceived organizational support and organizational citizenship behavior. *J. Appl. Psychol.* 105:1338. doi: 10.1037/apl0000481
143. Törnroos, M., Hintsanen, M., Hintsu, T., Jokela, M., Pulkki-Råback, L., Kivimäki, M., Keltikangas-Järvinen, L. (2012). Personality traits of the Five-Factor Model are associated with effort-reward imbalance at work: a population-based study. *Journal of Occupational and Environmental Medicine*, 54(7), 875–880. <https://doi.org/10.1097/JOM.0b013e31824fe0e4>
144. Törnroos, M., Hintsanen, M., Hintsu, T., Jokela, M., Pulkki-Råback, L., Hutri-Kähönen, N., & Keltikangas-Järvinen, L. (2013). Associations between Five-Factor Model traits and perceived job strain: a population-based study. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 18(4), 492-500.
145. Volmer, J., Niessen, C., Spurk, D., Linz, A. and Abele, A.E., 2011. Reciprocal Relationships between Leader-Member Exchange (LMX) and Job Satisfaction: A Cross-Lagged Analysis. *Applied Psychology*, 60(4), pp.522-545
146. Wang, Y., Kim, S., Rafferty, A., & Sanders, K. (2020). Employee perceptions of HR practices: A critical review and future directions. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 31(1), 128–173. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2019.1674360>
147. Wilkinson, A., Gollan, P.J., Marchington, M. & Lewin, D. (2010). Conceptualizing employee participation in organizations. In P. J. Gollan, D. Lewin, M. Marchington & A. Wilkinson, eds. *The Oxford handbook of participation in organizations*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, pp. 3–26.
148. Williams, L. J., & Anderson, S. E. (1991). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment as predictors of organizational citizenship and in-role behaviors. *Journal of Management*, 17(3), 601-617.
149. Woodman, R. W., Sawyer, J. E., & Griffin, R. W. (1993). Toward a theory of organizational creativity. *Academy of management review*, 18(2), 293-321.
150. Yang Fu and Zhang Lihua (2012). Organizational justice and perceived organizational support: The moderating role of conscientiousness in China. *Nankai Business Review International*. Volume: 1 Issue: 1, to Volume: 14 Issue: Retrieved from <https://www.emerald.com/insight/publication/issn/2040-8749>
151. Yukl, G. (2010) *Leadership in Organization*, Seventh Edition, Upper Saddle River, New Jersey, Pearson Education, Inc.